

Untangling FAIR Implementation in the Dutch SSH: the technical perspective

Work package 1 report

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Executive summary

This report is aimed at describing technical arrangements that can be used in FAIR data management within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domains, but is also informative for other scientific disciplines.

Examples of technical arrangements are services, tools and standards that are available to make data more FAIR, or to “FAIRify” data. The FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) forms the basis of the activities carried out. The FIP can be used to formalise FAIR implementation choices in the SSH domain.

The FIP is an excellent way to assess how a community applies the FAIR data principles. The FIP mini-questionnaire is an accessible tool for obtaining an initial overview of the FAIR enabling resources that formalize the FAIR principles and reveal where there are gaps. Formulating the community for which the FIP is relevant (the FIC, the FAIR Implementation Community) is less straightforward. It is challenging to formulate this in an unambiguous way. The FIP is part of the broader FIP Ecosystem, and understanding and determining its value for a specific community, organization, or service requires time and consultation. In any case, it can be concluded that a FIP can help to untangle the technical implementation of the FAIR principles in various ways.

The activities are carried out in relation to the project “Untangling FAIR Implementation in the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities”¹ funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) via the Thematic Digital Competence Centre Social Sciences & Humanities (TDCC-SSH). The Untangling FAIR project has also created an “Action Plan towards FAIR implementation in the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities” (Maineri, et al. 2026). The target audience of this report are policymakers, data stewards and researchers that are involved in activities to make or use FAIR data.

In the project practical work was done to create FIPs for communities in the SSH. It turned out that determining for which community (FIC) a FIP is relevant was not trivial. Four use-case were selected. Defining a FIC in general terms in an initial phase for the use-cases is not too difficult, but defining the FIC in a clear unambiguous way requires quite some effort. This is illustrated in this report. Eventually for one FIC (DANS Data Station SSH Managers) a detailed and extended FIP is created with the goal to act as a reference for all relevant FAIR aspects for this community. As standards and services that support the FAIR principles will continue to evolve in the future (with existing standards changing and new ones emerging), the FIP provides an overview of the state of affairs at a given point in time.

¹ See: <https://tdcc.nl/tdcc-ssh-bottleneck-projects/untangling-fair-implementation/>

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Introduction

Implementation of the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) principles in the SSH-domain suffers from misalignments along several dimensions between different stakeholders (e.g. Research, Infrastructure, Policy and Heritage). This report provides an overview of technical arrangements that are used in FAIR data management within the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain. Technical arrangements include a number of commonly used services and standards that are available for the application of the FAIR data principles: for instance, the FAIR principles can be implemented by connecting a persistent identifier (a PID such as a DOI) to a dataset (to make data Findable), by depositing a dataset in a repository like the DANS data station SSH (to make data Accessible), by using a standard data format such as xml (to make the data Interoperable) and by giving the dataset an Open Access license (to express how the data can be Reused). An example of an overview of practical tools and services that help to implement the FAIR principles is the “FAIR Implementation Catalogue”² by the FAIR-Impact project.

Nevertheless, the implementation of FAIR in the SSH is still in its infancy as technical and organisational complexity prevents the domain from taking full advantage of the highest standards for research data management. The aim of the Untangling FAIR project is to contribute to resolving this bottleneck. One of the project's work packages (WPs) concerns the “technical mapping” for FAIR data management within the SSH domain. The goal of the WP is to obtain a structured overview of the technical requirements for FAIR data management as stipulated by disciplinary (sub)communities, and map these to the stages of the research lifecycle. This report provides an overview of the activities and lessons learned in the WP. The FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP), which is designed to set out the choices relating to the implementation of the FAIR principles in the SSH domain forms the basis of this report.

The FIP Ecosystem is extensive and detailed, and the project aims to apply the principles of the FIP as comprehensively as possible in different use cases. An evaluation of the role of the FIP to “untangle” the FAIR Principles is part of the report.

What is a FIP?

A FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) is a collection of FAIR implementation choices made by a community of practice for each of the FAIR Principles. The implementation choices are made explicit by means of a questionnaire with questions addressing each of the FAIR Principles. The responses reflect technical choices agreed upon by a community, on how to implement the FAIR Principles. These choices are defined as FAIR Enabling Resources (FER). They put FAIR into action and are essential to the operationalisation of the FAIR principles.

² <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

This can be illustrated by the following example based on a random FIP survey question. With respect to the “Reusable” FAIR principle the FIP survey contains the question “Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?” A typical answer to this question would be the CC-BY-4.0³ (Open Access) license. The usage licence CC-BY-4.0 is the resource that operationalises the FAIR principle “(meta)data is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence”. The FIP questionnaire, see Figure 1, contains 22 questions, two of which concern usage licences as introduced above. A distinction is made between the FAIRness of data and the FAIRness of metadata, resulting in two questions (see the two questions “R1.1” in Figure 1). This distinction between data and metadata is applied consistently throughout the FIP questionnaire.

FAIR principle	Question
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?
F3	What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?
F4	In which registry are your metadata records indexed?
F4	In which registry are your datasets indexed?
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?
A2	Which metadata preservation policy do you use?
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?
R1.3	Who is the community, and what are their domain-relevant community standards?

Figure 1. 22 questions of the FIP questionnaire to express the implementation choices of the FAIR principles made by a FAIR implementation community⁴

A FIP can be used for three different purposes:

1. To create a reference FIP for a community as a FAIR policy to follow by each of the members of a community, or for other communities who want to connect to it;
2. To create a project or case-study specific FIP;
3. To create a digital object type specific FIP, e.g. for a Research Dataset.

A concise and extensive coverage of the different elements that support the creation and the use of FIPs is expressed in the FIP Ecosystem⁵ that can be consulted to get an overview of all relevant concepts and services. In this report components of the FIP Ecosystem are more detailed covered in case this is relevant to formalise FAIR implementation choices made in the Untangling FAIR project.

³ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

⁴ Location of FIP mini questionnaire to build your own FAIR Implementation Profile can be found at: <https://bit.ly/yourFIP>

⁵ <https://publish.obsidian.md/gff-concept-base/FIP+Ecosystem>

FAIR Supporting Resources

What are typical answers to the questions in the FIP questionnaire as provided in Figure 1? You can expect a specific metadata standard in response to a survey question regarding making data discoverable, a usage license to make data reusable, or a domain ontology to make data interoperable. These and other practices, policies, specifications and supporting technologies that make data FAIR are called “FAIR Supporting Resources” (FSR). A subclass of an FSR is a “FAIR Enabling Resource” (FER), that is linked to one or more of the FAIR principles. A number of FER types can be distinguished as is illustrated in Figure 2. The figure makes clear that a DOI⁶ is a FER of the type “identifier service” as an answer on the first question of the FIP questionnaire.⁷

FAIR principle	Question	FAIR enabling resource types	Your answers
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?	Identifier service	e.g. PURL, DOI
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?	Identifier service	
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	
F3	What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking schema	
F4	In which registry are your metadata records indexed?	Registry	
F4	In which registry are your datasets indexed?	Registry	
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation service	
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation service	
A2	Which metadata preservation policy do you use?	Metadata preservation policy	
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language	
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language	
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabulary	
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabulary	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Semantic model	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Semantic model	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license	
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	
R1.3	Who is the community, and what are their domain-relevant community standards?	FAIR Implementation Profile	

Figure 2. FIP questionnaire including FER types

FAIR Implementation Community (FIC)

An obvious question when completing the FIP questionnaire is to whom or what is the FIP relevant and intended, and which FSRs does this community use? For this the concept FAIR Implementation Community (FIC) is introduced, defined as a self-identified collection of people and/or organisations with the aim to implement the FAIR principles.⁸ A FIC can be mature or emerging.

The formulation of a FIC can be based on three foundations:

1. Type 1: User story (describes actions and desired outcomes from the perspective of a given user)
2. Type 2: Case study (real-life situation involving several actors and resources by communities of practice)

⁶ See: <https://www.doi.org/the-identifier/what-is-a-doi/>

⁷ An overview of the subclasses of a FER can be found at: <https://publish.obsidian.md/gff-concept-base/FER>

⁸ An overview of 10 rules that provide guidance and recommendations on how to start up discussions around implementation of FAIR can be found in: (Belliard, F. at. al. 2023).

- Type 3: Use case (generalized scenario derived from case studies trying to achieve the same objectives involving multiple actors and artefacts)

Further on in this report existing FICs, related to the SSH domain, are classified according to the foundations.

Creating the FIP: Questionnaire, Wizard and Nanopublication

Three systems are available to create a FIP for a FIC. First the FIP Questionnaire, which is a spreadsheet with questions about the FERs the user draws on. See Figure 1 and 2.⁹ Secondly, the FIP Wizard is an online tool that guides the user in the creation of a FIP.¹⁰ The FIP Wizard captures FIPs in a way that makes the FIPs themselves FAIR, e.g. by providing the FIP with different FERs, such as a PID, license, metadata, etc.. This “FAIR declaration” is added as question 23 to the FIP questionnaire. The FIP Wizard is an online data entry service (where the data entry fields are based on a knowledge model) that also can create nanopublications of FAIR declarations.¹¹ The third system is the nanopublication (or Nanopub), a small knowledge graph (in RDF) that is used to express a FIP declaration enabling FIPs to be published in a machine readable way. In the example below (Figure 3) the FAIR principle F4 (in which registry are your metadata records indexed - see Figure 1) is covered.¹²

The screenshot displays a Nanopublication interface for 'DANS Data Station-Social Science and Humanities (SSH)'. The interface shows a list of assertions with labels like 'DANS-Data-Station-SSH', 'url', 'type', 'comment', 'label', 'seeAlso', 'closeMatch', and 'has-target-group'. The 'comment' field contains a detailed description of the Data Station SSH. Below the assertions, there are fields for 'creator' (Shuai Wang) and 'wasDerivedFrom' (dataverse.org). At the bottom, it shows the creation date: '2024-01-30T14:03:30Z'.

Figure 3. Nanopublication expressing the FIP declaration that the “DANS Data Station SSH” is a FER of the type Registry¹³

⁹ See the 3PFF Conceptbase for context information on the FIP Questionnaire: <https://publish.obsidian.md/gff-concept-base/FIP+Questionnaire>

¹⁰ See: <https://fip.fair-wizard.com/>

¹¹ See: <https://publish.obsidian.md/gff-concept-base/FIP+Wizard>

¹² See: <https://publish.obsidian.md/gff-concept-base/Nanopublication>

¹³ The full unique identifier of this Nanopublication is: https://w3id.org/np/RA4_3a1OoOLirTVW1ZUDeV-qv8qCGZXcl8ACKZ3L1RMI. Nanodash is used to

FIPs and the SSH domain

This section provides an overview of the current situation regarding available FIPs in the Dutch SSH domain, the main focus area of the Untangling FAIR project. Several FIPs have already been drawn up in this area. These served as a starting point for further activities in the project, such as defining new FIPs and assessing their value for ‘untangling’ FAIR.

FAIR Connect¹⁴ is an online service that - among other things - contains an interactive overview of defined and published FIPs, FICs and FERs. The service shows that there are almost 900 FIPs published (with about 120 in the natural sciences as the discipline with the highest number of FIPs). FAIR Connect states that 26 FIPs are related to social sciences and humanities.¹⁵ Considering that the formulation of the FIC provides the basis for the further development of the FIP for this community, it is relevant to discuss this in more detail. Compiling a FIP starts with defining the community of practice for which decisions to implement the FAIR principles are expressed.

Figure 4 contains an overview of 9 prominent FICs in the SSH domain. The first 5 FICs are taken from the collection “FAIR Implementation Profiles for Social Science” (Wang, S. et. al., 2023). The overview does not claim to describe all available FICs in the SSH domain.

#	Title / Description	FIC Type
1	<i>Australian Social Survey International – European Social Survey (AUSSI-ESS)</i> ¹⁶	Case Study
	<i>“The Australian National University (ANU) conducted the ESS in an Australian context, under the title of the Australian Social Survey International – ESS (AUSSI-ESS). The purpose of the Australian study was to conduct a national study that enabled cross-continent comparisons to European countries that participate, to better understand the similarities and differences between countries. The fieldwork methodology for AUSSI-ESS was completed using self-completion of surveys via the web. This was different to that traditionally used in the ESS, which had used face-to-face survey methods almost exclusively through Wave 9.”</i>	
2	<i>The European Social Survey</i> ¹⁷	Case Study
	<i>“The European Social Survey (ESS) was established in 2001 to study the attitudes, beliefs and behaviours of the populations of European countries. In 2013, it was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium under EU legislation, and is one of the three ERICs in the social sciences.”</i>	
3	<i>GESIS Social Science Survey Research</i> ¹⁸	Case Study
	<i>“Data on Social Science survey research contained in the GESIS data catalogue. The data catalogue disseminates quantitative data - mostly from survey research - to a broad social science audience. In 2019 more than 14.000 individual users downloaded approx. 70.000 data files.”</i>	

create the nanopublication. Nanodash is a user-friendly web interface and API provider designed for creating, searching, and browsing nanopublications. See: <https://nanodash.knowledgepixels.com>

¹⁴ <https://fairconnect.pro/>

¹⁵ Status in January 2026.

¹⁶ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at: https://w3id.org/np/RAFjj8BMm_cJ8fdJtzakJJSwV21Vj4XWQmdQqtSvb3GUK

¹⁷ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at: http://purl.org/np/RAykrMeYjXsZsZx-pX4kOVdxxUbm7Ohz4fCk89dsHL_2o

¹⁸ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at: <http://purl.org/np/RARtgFtY0Xe6WqEiQCIFUvHT8Hv98-sQuz211I2BUclfk>

4	LGBTQ+ Linked Open Vocabulary Community ¹⁹	Use Case
	<i>"The LGBTQ+ Linked Open Vocabulary Community consists of researchers, librarians, linguistics experts that are contributing to the development and use of vocabularies such as Homosaurus, QLIT, etc. The community is centered around the Homosaurus project."</i>	
5	MCAL scholars - Media Content Analysis Lab scholars in the Netherlands ²⁰	User Story
	<i>"The Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) is funded by ODISSEI and it consists of scholars in the field of communication sciences and media content, largely based at the Amsterdam School of Communication Research (ASCoR) at the University of Amsterdam and at the Department of Social Sciences at Wageningen University. The MCAL seeks to tackle the major challenge of digital text analysis whereby copyright and GDPR restrictions make it very hard to share media content data by providing a workbench for researchers where they can share data and analyses with strict rights management, without the need to read or export the data themselves."</i>	
6	SSHOC-NL Socio-Economic History Community ^{21/22}	User Story
	<i>"The SSHOC-NL Socio Economic History (SEH) community consists of researchers in the Netherlands who conduct research and publish data about social history and economic history research. The community is led by researchers in the International Institute of Social History (IISG), as well as researchers in the Utrecht University, the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, RU Nijmegen, etc. The community is also actively involved in Dutch research infrastructures such as CLARIAH and ODISSEI (and their joint large infrastructure project starting in 2024, SSHOC-NL). As the name suggests, the SEH community spans different disciplines from the SSH, as it combines interests and expertise on history and historical data sources with the one on socio-economic aspects such as social inequalities and occupational dynamics."</i>	
7	CLARIN ²³	Use Case
	<i>"CLARIN is a digital infrastructure offering data, tools and services to support research based on language resources."</i>	
8	LISS Data Archive ²⁴	Case Study
	<i>"The LISS data archive community is the community of LISS panel that work on high-quality online research infrastructure in the Netherlands. All data obtained by studies in the LISS panel are published on the LISS Data Archive website."</i>	
9	The GLOBALISE Project Community ²⁵	Case Study
	<i>"GLOBALISE is a project of the Huygens Institute with the International Institute of Social History, the Digital Infrastructure Department of the KNAW Humanities Cluster, VU University, the University of Amsterdam, and the Dutch National Archives. It is funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO), grant no. 175.2019.003. Committed to enhancing the accessibility and research potential of the UNESCO Memory of the World-listed Dutch East India Company (VOC) archives, GLOBALISE has transcribed over 5 million handwritten pages and applies state-of-the-art AI methods to extract key entities, such as persons and places, as well as events from the texts. Reference data from secondary sources, collected and curated by project members, provides context to the entities and events."</i>	

Figure 4. Overview of existing FICs in the SSH domain

¹⁹ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at:

http://purl.org/np/RAOGUK-HzDHdTUPVG9tJXEjnG_p1mkqOylWUi10xf11_8

²⁰ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at:

http://purl.org/np/RAMrZ9OM8QJpE8W5d1OwHoNuUAOkD5jiwKAwd_m5eDqeo

²¹ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at:

https://w3id.org/np/RAXSiCvSYJ7hBxCDPi7IP8OXFX9ywj-Coz9klihRk8_Q8

²² Background information on this FIC and its related FIP and FERs can be found in: Wang, S., & Maineri, A. (2025).

²³ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at:

https://w3id.org/np/RAJ5ogFYmr0R1qUWsZ-faHYHdGMGaBgeKIU4j_PhF-9m0

²⁴ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at:

https://w3id.org/np/RAyWAZEGZ3vnaKWsHj0s5A4Zc9fcHWe_XCR_hlOOspDEU

²⁵ The nanopublication declaring this FIC can be found in Nanodash at:

https://w3id.org/np/RAZnynqcopFk4noz64JmLSke8wBhXX_w8tu_HY7Hn9J1s

On closer inspection, it appears that the names and descriptions of FICs differ in detail and that specific background knowledge is often required to properly understand the target group for which a FIP has been drawn up. The overview clearly shows that FICs are defined with varying degrees of detail and demarcation. Moreover, defining the FIC (that forms the basis of the FIP) requires intensive consultation with experts, data managers, researchers and other stakeholders related to the community as often knowledge is only implicitly available.

FIPs and the Untangling FAIR project

The Untangling FAIR project involved an investigation into the FIP Ecosystem as a tool for improving the FAIRness of research data. This included the implementation of practical applications, with the aim of determining the extent to which FIPs can assist in defining and embedding the FAIR principles within the SSH sector. Based on existing FIPs in the SSH domain (see overview in Figure 4) and consultation with representatives from the SSH network, four candidates were identified and invited to discuss the extent to which a FIP can assist in the practical implementation of the FAIR principles. The FIP mini-questionnaire formed the starting point for the discussion. The method used for this consisted of an analysis of available information (desk research) and a meeting with representatives of the community. The four use cases are covered in more detail in the appendix of this report.

Insights from the use-cases highlighted a number of challenges in drawing up comprehensive, reliable FIPs for Dutch SSH communities. This requires knowledge of aspects of the technical infrastructure used for storing and publishing (meta)data; this knowledge is often not available to FIC members. Furthermore, those involved faced time constraints when answering the questions, a problem that could not be resolved without additional resources. The WP1 team has therefore focused primarily on developing a FIP for a key infrastructure for data publication infrastructure for the Dutch social sciences and humanities: the DANS Data Station SSH. The other three FIPs are much less detailed and are based on a single exploratory meeting with representatives of the projects or organisations active in the SSH field.

FIPs and the Research Lifecycle

FIPs are useful to get snapshots of FAIR implementation in a community at a given moment, but the practice of research FAIR implementation is a continuous process, which takes place at various stages of the Research Data Lifecycle (see example in Figure 5). Some useful points emerged during the Community Writing Sprint and brought up in the “Action Plan towards FAIR Implementation in the Dutch SSH” (Maineri et al., 2026).

Figure 5: DDI Lifecycle Model

(Source: https://ddi-lifecycle-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/_images/DDILifecycle.jpg)

In particular, there was extensive discussion around the role of Data Management Plans (DMPs) (see Recommendation #3 in the Action Plan). While these are crucial instruments to ensure data collectors (e.g., researchers) think early about FAIR implementation, in practice these are often seen as an administrative burden. Moreover, the lack of integrated systems makes it so that researchers have to fill in information multiple times (e.g., ethics review forms, DMPs, metadata descriptions when publishing datasets, etc), exacerbating the risks of mistakes and failing to support appropriate event logging and versioning. Due to the nanopublication infrastructure, FIPs could play a role in improving the role of DMPs in research processes, and ensuring better service integration.

Some practical examples of this are: if, when drafting a DMP, it is known that the data will be deposited in the DANS data repository, the corresponding FIP could be retrieved automatically to provide suggestions regarding metadata schemas, file formats, licences, etc. (see, for example, Hettne et al., 2023 for a link between FIPs and DMPs). This would ease the burden on researchers and increase compliance with established and validated standards, as defined by a community of practice. For early work on this, see Singh et al. (2025). Conversely, DMPs could be used as input for creating FIPs, which would facilitate the reuse of FAIR implementation choices in the future and make it easier to link and align standards across communities.

Lessons learnt

The FIP guides you through the process of explicitly declaring what you do to make data and metadata FAIR. Tools, services (including training) and documentation are available to learn to create a FIP, but it takes a considerable amount of time to fully implement all components of the FIP Ecosystem in practice. It takes time to learn the “FIP language”, and to define and enforce a policy that establishes the role of the FIP for a specific target group, the FIC. Each FIP is a snapshot of the situation and, depending on its maturity and completeness, a policy for the future must be taken into account. Is drawing up the FIP a one-off activity or is a follow-up process agreed upon?

Both the FIP questionnaire and the FIP Wizard are not very strict when it comes to describing the FERs. Fields can be left blank, but with the intention of returning to them later.

The same FER can have different names.²⁶ This makes the FIP a living document that, if all goes well, will be supplemented and improved in the future. This is also supported by the fact that the FIP Wizard offers three choices when filling in the FAIR implementation choice: “a. Currently in use by the community, b. Currently in use, but is planned to be replaced in the future, and c. Is planned to be used in the future”. The explicit version declaration of the FIP also supports a long term commitment to maintain and improve the FIP by providing more and higher quality input on the FAIR implementation choices (and subsequently increment the version of the FIP).

The FIP journey begins with defining the “self-identified collection of people and/or organisations with the aim to implement the FAIR Principles”, the FIC. This process is highly dependent on communication with and involvement of people who represent this community. The FAIR principles can be applied to organizations, projects, services, and other constructs used by a community. Descriptions of existing FICs are not always easy to understand, even by experts active in the same scientific field. One of the key lessons learned from the Untangling FAIR project is that efforts must be made to clearly define which community the FIP is relevant to and what role the FIP plays in data management policies and procedures. It is not a given that completing a FIP mini-questionnaire will ultimately result in a complete and valid (expressed in RDF) project in the FIP Wizard.

Through hard work, feedback, and making choices (particularly in terms of detail and granularity), the Untangling FAIR project has begun to contribute to the knowledge base that brings all FERs together and makes them accessible to the outside world. This convergence is the point on the horizon that we had just reached in the project. But that is also the main reason to consider remaining involved in the FIP Ecosystem, not only in project form, but also structurally. By adding new FAIR-supporting resources to the knowledge base (available via FAIR Connect and as nanopubs in RDF format) and curating existing resources (improving their quality), the application of the FAIR principles will increase, both for people (who can reuse existing FIPs) and for machines that can process the machine-readable FAIR statements.

²⁶ For instance: "Dublin Core" and "Dublin Core Metadata" are the same FER. This is why FERs must be "curated". This can be done by certified Fellows. They have the authority to remove duplicate FSRs, standardize the names of FSRs and carry out other curation activities.

Appendix FIP Mini-questionnaires

This appendix contains four FIP mini-questionnaires drawn up during the project. The DANS FIP was developed through close consultation with the managers of the DANS Data Station SSH, the community (FIC) for which the FIP was drawn up. The FIPs of the other three communities should be regarded as a first step towards developing a more detailed FIP. The FAIR statements should be viewed with some caution, as not all stakeholders have been able to indicate which FAIR enabling resource types are missing or have been incorrectly assigned.

Furthermore, the wording of the FIC has not yet been definitively established. The use cases represent large organisations (Humanities Cluster, Faculty of Humanities Leiden University, Erasmus University) which, as communities, are too large to serve as a basis for a FIC. For this reason, a project, service or department was selected for which an initial draft of an FIP has been drawn, and which is included in this appendix. The FIP mini-questionnaires do not mention the names of data managers, as the project did not include feedback or further communication with the use cases. The DANS Data Station SSH FIP is an exception to this, as this FIP was drawn up in close consultation with the managers of the data stations.

FIP 1 - DANS Data Station SSH

The DANS Data Station SSH²⁷ is a service that enables researchers to deposit and search data in the social sciences and humanities. In consultation with data station managers, a FIC has been defined for which a comprehensive FIP has been drawn up with help of the FIP Wizard; this process took up a significant portion of the time available to the Untangling FAIR project. The output from the FIP Wizard is published (van Horik, R., Braukmann, R., & Touber, J. (2026)).

~ FIP mini-questionnaire ~

Community description	
Name of Community	DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities
Description of Community	This FIP is created by the managers of the DANS Data Station SSH and provides an overview of the FAIR Implementation Choices of the DANS Data Station SSH.
Supporting Links	https://ssh.datastations.nl
Research Domain	Social Sciences and Humanities
Data Steward	--
Date of FIP creation	2026

FAIR principle	Question	FAIR enabling resource types	Your answers
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²⁷ See: <https://ssh.datastations.nl/>

F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?	Identifier service	DOI
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?	Identifier service	DataCite DOI, URN:NBN
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	Dublin Core, DDI Codebook, DataCite Metadata Scheme, Schema.org (dataset), OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives, OAI-ORE, DCAT-AP, Croissant Metadata format
F3	What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking schema	RO-Crate
F4	In which registry are your metadata records indexed?	Registry	DANS Data Station SSH, OpenAIRE Research Graph, Google Dataset Search, Google Search, Harvard Dataverse Repository, B2FIND, DataCite Commons, Mendelay Data, ODISSEI Portal, CESSDA Data Catalogue, CLARIN VLO, Getuigenverhalen, CLARIAH Media Suite,
F4	In which registry are your datasets indexed?	Registry	DANS Data Station SSH
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	REST, HTTPS, OAI-PMH, SWORD, Dataverse API
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	REST, HTTPS, SWORD, Dataverse API
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation service	
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation service	SURFconext, Gmail Log in, ORCID-AAI, Dataverse Access Request Service, Github Login
A2	Which metadata preservation policy do you use?	Metadata preservation policy	DANS Data Stations Policy, CoreTrustSeal
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language	JSON-LD, Croissant Metadata Format, OAI-ORE, DataCite Metadata Schema, OpenAIRE Metadata Schema for Data Archives, DDI-Codebook, Dublin Core Metadata Element Set, JSON,
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use	Knowledge representation language	PDF, TXT, HTML, NetCDF, CSV, SPSS, Stata Data File Format, R File Format, JPEG, TIFF, PNG, ASCII, LASer File Format, LAZ File Format, RDF, Turtle Format, JSON-LD, REFI-QDA

	for datasets?		standard, Open Document Format, XML, Markdown, Matlab, Text-Fabric, Open Document Format, SQL, SIARD, DICOM, JASP, SVG, BWF, MXF, Matroska Multimedia Container, FLAC, OPUS, AutoCAD DXF, GML, MIF/MID, GeoTIFF, ASCII GRID, WaveFront, PLY, X3D, GIF 2.0, COLLADA File Format, IFC, TriG, N-Triples Format
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabulary	CESSDA Topic Classification, NARCIS Classification of Scientific Disciplines, Dataverse Subject Terms, ISO 639-2:1998, ISO 3166-1:2013, DDI Controlled Vocabularies, AAT, ELSST, Goenames Ontology, ROR, DANS Identifiers Type, DANS Contributor, DANS Personal Data, DANS Relations
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabulary	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Semantic model	DANS Data Station SSH Metadata Template
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Semantic model	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license	CC0 1.0
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license	CC0 1.0, CC BY 4.0, DANS License, CC BY SA 4.0, CC BY-NC 4.0, CC BY-ND 4.0, CC BY-NC-ND 4.0, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, BSD 2-Clause "Simplified" License, BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" License, MIT License, Apache 2 Software License, CeCILL Free Software License Agreement, CeCILL-B Free Software License Agreement, GPL-3.0-only GNU General Public License, LGPL-3.0-or-later GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0 or later, Mozilla Public License (MPL) v2.0, TAPR Open Hardware License v1.0, CERN Open Hardware License 1.1, GPL-2.0-or-later GNU Public License v2.0 or later
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	Dataverse Support for Dataset Versions
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	Dataverse Support for Dataset Versions
R1.3	Who is the community, and what are their domain-relevant community standards?	FAIR Implementation Profile	

The DANS Data Station SSH FIP serves as a central knowledge base, where all decisions regarding the FAIR principles applied in the DANS Data Station SSH are formulated, updated, and shared. For the purposes of the project, making a FIP for the DANS Data Station SSH creates a basis for many other research communities in the Netherlands who use the platform to share their data, allowing them to be more aware of which kinds of FAIR Implementation choices are supported by this infrastructure. This contributes to untangle FAIR implementation in the domain by making technical arrangements more explicit and accessible to others. Moreover, as other platforms also describe their FERs in FIPs, connecting repositories to each other becomes easier over time. Overall, FIPs increase the Interoperability across the communities they describe.

A couple of alternatives are available for the DANS Data Station SSH to define the community (FIC) for which the FIP can formalize FAIR declarations.²⁸ Examples are: the users of the data station, the depositors of data in the data station or the data station itself as a service. In consultation with the data station manager it was decided to define a FIP based on the user story: “As data station manager, I want to showcase how our Data Station implements the FAIR principles in a structured and machine-readable way so that depositors know the FAIR policies of the Data Station.” Based on this user story the FIC can be described as *“This FIP is created by the managers of the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to provide an overview of the FAIR Implementation Choices of the DANS Data Station SSH.”* The FIP will contain the FAIR Enabling Resources (FER) relevant for the data station managers.²⁹ The DANS Data Station SSH FIP could serve as a central knowledge base in the future, where all decisions regarding the FAIR principles applied in the DANS Data Station SSH are formulated, updated, and shared. Before that happens, the FIP must first be developed, of course.

The first step to create the DANS Data Station SSH FIP was to fill in the FIP mini-questionnaire (See Figure 1 and Figure 2). Several of the questions could be answered without much effort, such as the DOI as one of the (quite obvious) Identifier Services to cover FAIR principle F1. Other questions required more effort, and at times also the formulation of new FERs (in the form of a nanopublication).

With regard to the FIP question on data interoperability (I1), “Which knowledge representation language (enabling machine interoperability) do you use for datasets?” the file formats that DANS considers durable are the answer to this question. As this list of “preferred data formats” is available as a PDF document³⁰ (thus not “FAIR” at all) it was decided to create for each preferred file format a separate FER (in the form of a

²⁸ In Figure 3 the DANS Data Station is expressed as a FER of the type Registry. This differs from the way in which the FIP is formulated in the project. This can be confusing, because there is a FER (Registry) and an FIP with the almost the same name: “DANS Data Station SSH”. In FAIR Connect, this distinction is visible.

²⁹ The nanopublication that defines the FIC “Managers DANS Data Station SSH” can be found at: <https://w3id.org/np/RA508adujnSK418WRLX5OqfUeWh5cA0pqc3UqXyMGhaeU>

³⁰ See: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

nanopublication) of the type “knowledge representation language”³¹. For this the FIP Wizard was used. It was good to discover that nanopublications were already available for many data file formats that are part of the DANS list of preferred data formats, illustrating the potential value of creating and sharing (and curating) nanopublications.

The same process was done with respect to the FIP question on data reusability (R1.1) “Which usage license do you use for your datasets?” Nanopublications are available for various licenses, so that they do not need to be declared again, but a new nanopublication has been created for the specific “DANS data license”³².

Other FSRs that were created were nanopublications of “subject Lists” used by the DANS data station as “Structured Vocabulary” related to the Interoperability (I2) question “Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?” and the “DANS data station policy”³³

The creation of the FIP has contributed to making the DANS Data Station SSH more FAIR, for example by extracting FAIR Supporting Resources from PDF documents into separate nanopublications that are considered more sustainable and are FAIR by design. But this is only the first step, as policies and procedures need to be developed to integrate and update FIPs in the long term. In practice, this means, for example, that it is no longer the PDF document with the list of preferred data formats that is leading, but the separate nanopublications that each reflect a preferred data format, that in turn means that keeping track of and updating the information in the nanopublications must be part of the organization's work routine.

³¹ A random example is the GLTF 2.0 file format, for 3D data sets, see: https://w3id.org/np/RA9H_uwgeeV6r_FGwXg6p-Fr6uemQLGzoTApRZCuIRVDU

³² The Nanopublication of the DANS License can be found at: https://w3id.org/np/RAA6xLBbyYc4I7HOXF8Lck_bHyiezo9f1IN0OIYXI_2Dc

³³ Again initially available in PDF format: <https://dans.knaw.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/DANS-Data-Stations-Policy.pdf>

FIP 2 - KNAW Humanities Cluster (HuC)

The KNAW Humanities Cluster (HuC) consists of a number of institutes, labs, infrastructures and projects³⁴. One of the institutes is the International Institute of Social History³⁵ that is involved in the creation of the FIP “SSHOC-NL Socio-Economic History Community” (See: Figure 4). In communication with data managers of the Huygens Institute³⁶, also part of Huc, a first version of a FIP was defined by using the FIP mini-questionnaire, aimed at archivists that deal with the research data. Further communication is required to improve the quality and completeness of this FIP.

~ FIP mini-questionnaire ~

Community description			
Name of Community		Humanities Cluster (HuC)	
Description of Community		FIP targeted at archivists of the Huygens Institute (part of HuC)	
Supporting Links		https://huc.knaw.nl	
Research Domain		(digital) humanities	
Data Steward		--	
Date of FIP creation		July 2025	
FAIR principle	Question	FAIR enabling resource types	Your answers
F3	What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking mechanism	
F4 (MD)	Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?	Registry	Dataverse / eDepot Archivematica / ATOM
F4 (D)	Which service do you use to publish your datasets?	Registry	Dataverse / eDepot Archivematica / ATOM
A1.1 (MD)	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	REST / HTTPs / OAI-PMH
A1.1 (D)	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	REST / HTTPs
A1.2 (MD)	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation service	SURFconext, Google account, Github, ORCID
A1.2 (D)	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation service	
A2	What metadata preservation policy do you use?	Metadata preservation policy	CoreTrustSeai
I1 (MD)	What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use	Knowledge representation	JSON LD, Schema.org

³⁴ The website of the KNAW Humanities Cluster can be found at: <https://huc.knaw.nl/>.

³⁵ <https://iisg.amsterdam/en>

³⁶ <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/>

	for metadata records?	language	
<u>I1 (D)</u>	What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language	
<u>I2 (MD)</u>	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies	AAT and other thesauri
<u>I2 (D)</u>	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabularies	
<u>I3 (MD)</u>	What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?	Semantic model	
<u>I3 (D)</u>	What semantic model do you use for your datasets?	Semantic model	
<u>R1.1 (MD)</u>	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Usage license	Creative commons
<u>R1.1</u>	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Usage license	Creative commons
<u>R1.2 (MD)</u>	What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	
<u>R1.2 (D)</u>	What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	

FIP 3 - Faculty of Humanities Leiden University

For the Faculty of Humanities of Leiden University, the focus was on the LeiLanD (Leiden Language Data) information system.³⁷ This is a searchable catalogue containing basic metadata information about linguistic data collected by researchers at Leiden University. Some of the datasets are openly available online. For those that have restricted access it is possible to contact the dataset creators for access.³⁸

~ FIP mini-questionnaire ~

Community description	
Name of Community	Leiden Language Data (LeiLanD)
Description of Community	Leiden University Centre for Linguistics (LUCL) initiated Leiland, a searchable catalogue containing basic metadata information about linguistic data collected by researchers at Leiden University. Some of the datasets are openly available online. For those that have restricted access it is possible to contact the dataset creators for access.
Supporting Links	https://leiland.lucdh.nl
Research Domain	Linguistics
Data Steward	--
Date of FIP creation	July 2025

FAIR principle	Question	FAIR enabling resource types	Your answers
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?	Identifier service	Handle
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?	Identifier service	Handle
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	CMDI (profile "Corpus Collection") LeiLanD metadata fields Dublin Core
F3	What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking schema	

³⁷ <https://leiland.lucdh.nl>

³⁸ For the compilation of this FIP information is used from Sanders, et al (2024).

F4	In which registry are your metadata records indexed?	Registry	https://github.com/handyc/leiland (Django app) CLARIN VLO Collection Bank
F4	In which registry are your datasets indexed?	Registry	
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	OAI-PMH, HTTPS
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation service	
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation service	
A2	Which metadata preservation policy do you use?	Metadata preservation policy	
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language	CMDI (profile "Corpus Collection")
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language	CSV, Excel
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabulary	ISO 639-2, ISO 639-3, Glottocode
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabulary	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Semantic model	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Semantic model	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license	
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	
R1.3	Who is the community, and what are their domain-relevant community standards?	FAIR Implementation Profile	

FIP 4 - Erasmus University School of Social and Behavioral Sciences

A use-case from the social sciences was provided by Erasmus University that is a member of the GUTS (Growing Up Together) consortium³⁹. The GUTS program brings together an interdisciplinary team of researchers that investigates youth from the perspective of societal neuroscience, and combines insights from neuroscience, psychology, psychiatry, and sociology. For the GUTS project an extensive Data Management Plan (DMP) is available. The research data is not open available and stored in federated Yoda registries. For MRI data the BIDS standard (<https://bids.neuroimaging.io>) is used in which imaging data is accompanied by machine-readable metadata in sidecar JSON files. The GUTS codebook (<https://guts-consortium.github.io/guts-rdm/codebook.html>) contains an overview of which measures are collected by which cohort(s).

~ FIP mini-questionnaire ~

Community description	
Name of Community	Growing Up Together in Society (GUTS) consortium
Description of Community	<i>The GUTS consortium investigates youth from the perspective of societal neuroscience, and combines insights and expertise from neuroscience, psychology, psychiatry, and sociology. The consortium is funded by a Gravitation grant from the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science for a ten-year period (2023-2033). In the GUTS project, data will be collected from different longitudinal cohorts at different locations in the Netherlands. This will encompass magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data, questionnaire data (e.g. behavioral and social measures), and genetic data. A number of similar measures will be collected across all cohorts.</i>
Supporting Links	https://www.gutsproject.com
Research Domain	Societal neuroscience
Data Steward	---
Date of FIP creation	"July 2025"

FAIR principle	Question	FAIR enabling resource types	Your answers
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?	Identifier service	DOI (minted via YODA)
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?	Identifier service	DOI (minted via YODA)

³⁹ <https://www.gutsproject.com/home/>

F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	for MRI data the BIDS standard (https://bids.neuroimaging.io) is used in which imaging data is accompanied by machine-readable metadata in sidecar JSON files. / The GUTS codebook (https://guts-consortium.github.io/guts-rdm/codebook.html) contains an overview of which measures are collected by which cohort(s).
F3	What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking schema	DataCite / YODA
F4	In which registry are your metadata records indexed?	Registry	YODA workspaces (4 locations)
F4	In which registry are your datasets indexed?	Registry	YODA workspaces (4 locations)
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	The way that data is structured within GUTS results in metadata being present in three different ways. In the name of the file (file naming conventions) In the folder location In an accompanying file (e.g. a .JSON file) https://guts-consortium.github.io/guts-rdm/metadata.html
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	OAI-PMH / HTTPS
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation service	YODA user/password
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation service	YODA user/password
A2	Which metadata preservation policy do you use?	Metadata preservation policy	
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language	JSON / BIDS standard
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language	GUTS data consists of various data types and formats. An overview of all data formats during the two phases (raw / processed) of data processing https://guts-consortium.github.io/guts-rdm/data-formats.html
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata	Structured vocabulary	

	records?		
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabulary	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Semantic model	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Semantic model	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license	https://www.gutproject.com/data/
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license	https://www.gutproject.com/data/
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	
R1.3	Who is the community, and what are their domain-relevant community standards?	FAIR Implementation Profile	

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